

IMPORTANCE OF USING VISUAL AIDS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE FOR BEGINNERS

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Annotation: The purpose of this study is to highlight the importance of visual aids in teaching English language for beginners to grasp more attention of learners and provide them with deep and precise understanding of the topic. Experienced teachers try to conduct the lesson with the help of more authentic materials mostly for those who has less attention span particularly from the 1st to -4th grade. This article shed the lights on proper usage of realia materials providing scientists viewpoints.

Key words: visual aids, teaching, young learners, skills, methods.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching English is becoming significantly essential for the last decades since the future of young generation is highly likely to depend on more advanced way of living. The reliance on more qualified teaching methods will be high and directed on conducting lessons with the help of visual materials is in demand. Undoubtedly, the attention span of young learners is shorter in comparison with older people therefore if the teacher uses the simple method of teaching only by reading the exercises from the book, the child feels bored and cannot understand the topic and loses interest from the beginning. However, if the lesson is more colorful and designed with the material from real life, learners might feel more curious which means they start to pay attention. Moreover, Domin (2007) [2] study which was done in Cambridge University about application of visual aids in teaching English, argues that since ancient times man has always made visual representation of reality and used visual stimuli to transmit information. Ever since the times of our ancestors the existence of visual aids have been used and the evidence for this can be the drawings on the walls of pre-historic caves. To transfer the data from one generation to another, they used possible ways such as leaves of trees, most commonly building blocks and walls which were from rocks, they carved and left their way of living style with pictures and this way first alphabet letters started to appear.

Furthermore, Linz (1991) [3] under UNESCO carried out a research on the development of audio-visual education in Kenya and his research findings commented that the visual are important in English language because their value is appraised according to their facility in assisting teachers to teach children and in assisting children to learn. In addition, if the realia to the topic such as about animals, body parts, colors, fruits & vegetables is implemented whether in online or with pictures this may lead to long-term memorization. The features of authentic material are useful not only in teaching vocabulary but also in explaining grammar and in other skills of English language such as (writing, speaking, reading, listening).

How to use visual aids and its importance in Skills of English Language

The benefits of realia in teaching writing skill for beginners is crucial due to the fact that, they do not have misunderstandings about the topic when they see the thing in front, cause at

the very beginning learners do not tend to write complex essay which require cognitive function and proper structure instead they start by easier techniques and questions asking to describe the picture or thing. Domin (2007) [2] in her research done in UK in Cambridge University on Application of Visuals in English Teaching asserts that, today we live in highly visual world, dominated by visual messages. In fact, we are surrounded by visuals aids, pictures demonstrating us information about every day news and updates, advertisements about various products and services make us aware of changes.

The usage of visual aids in teaching speaking, nowadays even the tests of qualification certificate have the sessions of picture describing, by looking to the picture they should describe it for the given certain minute. According to the United Republic of Tanzania under the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training (2010) [4], a research was carried out on Pedagogy and leadership in Tanzanian primary school, findings illustrated that, visual when properly used in language teaching brings about learners' communicative competence.

The listening skill also highlights the need for authentic material since before listening the track or audio they should be provided with instructions and strategies first, such as pre, while and post listening. In the pre-stage, especially beginner learners need clear explanation therefore teachers should teach them to look and understand the topic then predict about what the listening audio is going to be. To explain the topic deeply the need for realia is highlighted again. Calder (2008) [1] conducted a case study on the selection and evaluation of audio-visual media to supporting language learners in South Africa. The research data showed that, visual-media has important role in supporting English language teaching because they stimulate cognitive skills including solving critical thinking.

The part of receptive skills is reading which is challenging when it comes to young learners because they are lack of vocabulary range when the long paragraph and short stories are given, hence, the role of visuals is necessary to reveal the meaning of the text. Furthermore, young learners demonstrate more enthusiasm when they see a story with their favorite actors and celebrities from cartoons and engage in lesson. Therefore, if the instructor brings texts relevant to the topic and with well-known heroes' demonstrations, they will see the higher level of interest in child to get the information about the character they know.

To sum up, this study examined the valuable aspects of the use of visual aids in the English language acquisition. The research focused on basic utilization of realia material in correlated 4 skills of English language in the classroom of mostly primary school.

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